

Main category	Sub category
Adoption of the intervention: the eCRF	Usage Entering data into the eCRF Effort Technical problems
Adoption of the intervention: the CMR	Usage Experiences with the patient Expenditure of time Evaluation of the CMR
Adoption of the recommendations	Medication changes Barriers Other effects resulting from the CMR
Future implementation	Future utilization Enhancing factors Hindering factors